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The Importance of Good Health for Academic Success

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Students have other obligations apart from doing assignments, projects, and paperwork. Some college students work part-time to help their families lessen the burden of paying tuition. A student's life is not like the one in movies where they have everything they need; not everyone is fortunate to have that kind of life. In other words, each student has a story to tell. Asking these working students to choose between working and studying is not a simple decision for them to make. It is indeed challenging to study and work at the same time; balancing these two things requires time management. With that, students have no choice but to sacrifice their sleep to finish those activities. So how much more for working students who usually study in the morning and work at night? It is twice as hard for them to live with that schedule.

There are other reasons why students pull an all-nighter besides finishing a ton of schoolwork. One is because of social media. It is used to watch YouTube videos, browse recent news, and communicate with friends. There are many applications available to them that are addictive. One of them is TikTok, which provides funny videos shared by users from all around the world. A person can spend their entire day on TikTok without getting bored. Another is video games. Video games are designed to entertain people, which is why many kids become addicted to them. However, too much exposure to social media can lead to many health issues. Even though TikTok has many entertaining videos, some contents are not for children to see. Failure to protect kids from malicious content on social media may lead to serious behavioral problems. Bullying in video games frequently happens too. Speaking inappropriately and offensively to one another can lead to low self-esteem and, in the worst-case scenario, violence toward others. If parents limit their screen time, it will not only keep them away from these circumstances but also help them complete their sleep and improve their focus. Cramming is also one of the top reasons why students stay up late at night. To avoid too much workload on the plate, good time management is the key. Doing homework weeks before the deadline helps avoid cramming and stress. Skipping meals is not advisable too. Doing all the things mentioned results in not having enough rest and being prone to sickness. High grades are useless if the body is too weak to move the next day.

Having a healthy mind and body contributes to academic success. Studying will surely take most of a student's time in a day which gives more reasons to include health in the priorities. Healthy living is always part of attaining academic achievement. Every

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student must remember that nothing is more significant than ensuring the body is healthy.

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